

**THE FIRST INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC-PRACTICAL VIRTUAL
CONFERENCE IN HEALTH INNOVATIONS & RESEARCH:
PROGNOSIS, ACHIEVEMENT, AND CHALLENGES.**

CONFERENCE PROCEEDINGS

AZERBAIJAN-ESTONIA-KAZAKHSTAN-TURKEY

ESTONIA, TALLINN DECEMBER 15-16, 2023

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TALLINN 2023

Organizer of the conference:

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University Clinic for pediatric diseases, department of neurology Skopje.

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Namig Isazade

International Research, Education & Training Center. MTÜ. PhD in Business Administration.

Nino Didbaridze

Tbilisi State Medical University. Microbiology and Immunology Department. Immunology Direction. PhD MD.

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Doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor, Department of Anesthesiology and Reanimatology, West Kazakhstan Marat Ospanov Medical University

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PROGRAM AT A GLANCE

First day	15 December 2022
Moderators	Namig Isazade, Aytan Huseynova
Opening ceremony	Namig Isazade
19.00-19.20	Zhansulu Sarkulova Doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor, West Kazakhstan Marat Ospanov Medical University.
	Tamar Giorgadze Assistant Professor, Tbilisi State Medical University.
	Tamara Abayeva Kyrgyz State Medical Academy named after I.K. Akhunbaev.
19.20-19.40	Tamara Quliyeva SÜD VƏZİ XƏRÇƏNGİNİN MÜALİCƏSİNDƏ «İNVIŞİBLE SURGERY» ANLAYIŞI.
19.40-20.00	Sarkulova Zh.N., Tokshilykova A.B., Sarkulov M.N., Daniyarova K.R., Kalieva B.M., Zhankulov M.H. ENDOTHELIAL GLYCOCALYX DAMAGE IN PATIENTS WITH SEVERE FUNCTIONAL INJURY.
20.00-20.20	Tamar Giorgadze, Sophy Giorgadze MITOCHONDRIA – AS A TARGET OF ENVIRONMENTAL FACTORS.
20.20-20.40	Erekle Mosidze, Ana Chikovani CURRENT METHODS OF TREATMENT OF SUNKEN CHEST.
20.40-21.00	Т.С. Абаева, М.Т. Жанганаева, З.Тойчиева ХАРАКТЕРИСТИКА ИММУННОГО СТАТУСА В ЭТАПЕ ВОЗРАСТНОЙ ИНВОЛЮЦИИ У ЛЮДЕЙ.
21.00-21.20	Leartha Alili Ademi NEUROLOGICAL ASSESSMENT IN CHILDREN WITH CHROMOSOMAL DISORDERS: CASE SERIES PRESENTATION.
21.20-21.40	Шафаг Асадова, Шарифа Вагабова, Рена Гурбанова, Фарида Аббасова, Шафа Амирасланова КЛИНИКО-ДИАГНОСТИЧЕСКИЕ ОСОБЕННОСТИ ПОСТМЕНО-ПАУЗАЛЬНОГО ОСТЕОПОРОЗА У ЖЕНЩИН В УСЛОВИЯХ г. БАКУ.
21.40-22.00	Л.И.Аллахвердиева, Н.М.Гулиева, З.У.Мамедова КОРРЕЛЯЦИЯ МЕЖДУ КАЧЕСТВОМ ЖИЗНИ И ТЯЖЕСТЬЮ ЗАБОЛЕВАНИЯ ПЕДИАТРИЧЕСКИХ ПАЦИЕНТОВ С АТОПИЧЕСКИМ ДЕРМАТИТОМ.
22.00-22.20	Nodar Sulashvili, Shafiga Topchiyeva, Vira Kravchenko, Diego Rada Fernandez de Jauregui, Luiza Gabunia, Nana Gorgaslidze, Tamar Tsintsadze, Nino Abuladze, THE SCIENTIFIC TALKS OF CHARACTERISTICS OF SOME KEY ISSUE ASPECTS OF PHARMACISTS' PROFESSION, VOCATIONAL ACHIEVEMENTS, ENHANCEMENT, CHALLENGES, INCLINATION AND PERSPECTIVES IN PHARMACEUTICS AND MEDICINE BASED ON THE SUNLIGHT OF SOCIAL PHARMACY AT LOCAL AND GLOBAL LEVEL IN GENERAL.
22.20-22.40	Melis Gönülal, Didem Didar Balci USING IXEKIZUMAB AND OMALIZUMAB AT THE SAME TIME: A CASE WITH PSORIASIS AND CHRONIC IDIOPATHIC URTICARIA.
22.40-23.00	Nodar Sulashvili, Kakhaber Robakidze, Ketevan Chakhnashvili, Irma Buchukuri, Lela Grigolia, Veriko Khundzakishvili, Nato Alavidze, Tamar Okropiridze, Igor Seniuk THE SCIENTIFIC TALKS OF THE FEATURES RATIONAL ANTIBIOTIC PHARMACOTHERAPY, PHARMACODYNAMICS OF SOME ANTIBIOTICS' AND ANTIBIOTIC RESISTANCE IN MICROBES OF BACTERIAL DISEASES OF THE MUCOUS MEMBRANES AND SKIN OF THE ORAL CAVITY IN GENERAL THERAPEUTIC STRATEGIES AND FUTURE PROSPECTS.

ABSTRACTS AND THESES

SOCIO-DEMOGRAPHIC AND CLINICAL FEATURES OF DRUG USERS UNDER TREATMENT AT THE REPUBLICAN POISON CENTER IN CONNECTION WITH DRUG OVERDOSE

¹Bilal Asadov, ²Pervin Mamedov, ³Nesimi Vahabov

¹Department of Psychiatry of AMU, Doctor of Medicine, professor,

²Saatli district Central hospital Public Right Person, General Director,

³Department of Psychiatry of AMU, assistant

ABSTRACT

The presented article presents the results of a study of the socio-demographic and clinical characteristics of 532 drug users, residents of Baku, who were treated at the Republican Toxicology Center in connection with an overdose of narcotic substances. It was revealed that among the surveyed population the ratio of men and women was 1:7, the prevalence of young people with secondary education, not working, having a family and unmarried, mainly residents of the Yasamal, Nasimi and Binagadi districts of Baku. A study of the drug history of 197 patients showed that most of them had been using drugs for 1 to 2 years, mainly opiates (heroin, coconut) by injection. In the majority of those examined, the cause of overdose was the desire to enhance the euphoric effect of narcotic drugs and relapse after treatment. Most patients had a comatose state of varying severity, respiratory and palpitation disturbances, and obstructive disorders. In this regard, patients are connected to artificial respiration. The **Mindray SV300 ventilator** is suitable for both adults and children. It is used for invasive and non-invasive methods of artificial lung ventilation and is mainly applied in intensive care units. During intensive therapy, in most patients, the signs of acute poisoning were relieved within 1-12 days; 34 patients, despite therapeutic measures, died.

Keywords: socio-demographic and clinical characteristics, narcotic substances.

CURRENT METHODS OF TREATMENT OF SUNKEN CHEST

¹Erekle Mosidze, ²Ana Chikovani, ³Manana Giorgobiani

¹MD, PhD student, ²Medical Resident, ³MD, PhD, Professor

^{1,3}David Aghmashenebeli University of Georgia.

ABSTRACT

Sunken chest, also called funnel chest, is the most common deformation of the sternum, which is caused by the posterior depression of the sternum and lower costal cartilages. Deformation determines the reduction of the space of the chest cavity and the restriction of the functioning of the organ systems, cardiovascular and respiratory systems in this cavity, which causes the severity of the pathology. Prevalence is 1/300 to 1/1000 live births. 1/5 - female/male, 90% of chest wall deformities are sunken chest. Most of the cases appear in the first year of life. A funnel-shaped chest is formed during puberty. Funnel chest may be present as an isolated anomaly or as a part of various congenital pathologies. Among congenital clinical syndromes, connective tissue diseases are very rare (less than 1%).

Sunken chest etiopathogenesis, genetic factors, associated diseases are diverse and are still the subject of study. Due to the fact, that we have a little information on the etiological factors, and the said deformation and the degree of deformation, determine the pathological functioning of the cardiovascular and respiratory systems, the treatment of deformation is the most urgent, complex and developing issue. Our goal is to present different treatment techniques, discuss and compare treatment method, which is introduced in Georgia.

Treatment methods

The degree of deformation, which is calculated by the "Haller index", and the severity of the disease determine the treatment method. Surgical intervention is the main method of treatment during the development of a sunken chest, however, in the case of a mild degree of the mentioned deformation, other and different approaches are used.

Over two centuries, many surgical techniques have been developed. Some of them are used today.

Invasive interventions:

Ravitch's technique (1949) - modified by Fonkalsrud is an open surgical intervention. The technique is a massive invasive surgical intervention. Reparative procedures involving cartilage resection are straightforward in the 2- to 5-year-old age group, although later-onset chest wall malformations are common after similar interventions at this age, resulting in reduced chest cavity space. The severity of the pathology caused by the mentioned defect is equal to cardiopulmonary disorders caused by a funnel chest. Therefore, Ravitch's technique is mostly used in practice after puberty, although the technique and the results of the intervention, it is also appropriate from the age of 10.

Result: after the operation, the patient stays in the clinic for 7 days. The main factor why it remains under the care of a doctor is pain and pleural effusion. After discharge, treatment with anti-inflammatory, pain-relieving drugs continues. The patient is warned not to lie on his side for 3 weeks. The patient is recommended to do deep breathing exercises several times a day. After 3 months, light aerobic exercises can be started. After 6 months of upper body lifting.

Fonkalsrud described 275 patients over a 3-year period who underwent surgery with a similar approach. It should be noted that except for 5 patients, all had good results, without serious complications or fatal outcomes.

Main intraoperative complication: pneumothorax.

Post-operative complications: wound infection, seroma formation.

Keywords: pneumothorax, wound infection, seroma formation.

USING IXEKIZUMAB AND OMALIZUMAB AT THE SAME TIME: A CASE WITH PSORIASIS AND CHRONIC IDIOPATHIC URTICARIA

¹Melis Gönülal, ²Didem Didar Balcı

^{1,2}University of Health Sciences, İzmir Tepecik Training and Research Hospital, Department of Dermatology, İzmir, Turkey.

ABSTRACT

Here we want to present our case using ixekizumab for his moderate plaque psoriasis and omalizumab for his chronic idiopathic urticaria at the same time. A 65-year-old male patient with hypertension and dyslipidemia used omalizumab and ixekizumab in combination for 9 months and any adverse effects were observed. The patient continues his treatments because he benefits from these treatments. According to different works and case reports, omalizumab can be used with any other biological agent safely in psoriasis patients. Nonetheless, long-term studies on efficacy and safety in real-life treatment settings are needed.

Keywords: psoriasis, chronic idiopathic urticaria, ixekizumab, omalizumab.

NEUROLOGICAL ASSESSMENT IN CHILDREN WITH CHROMOSOMAL DISORDERS: CASE SERIES PRESENTATION

¹Learta Alili Ademi, ²Blerim Ademi, ³Elena Sukarova-Angelovska

^{1,2,3}University Clinic for pediatric diseases, department of neurology Skopje

ABSTRACT

Neurological assessment presents a series of tests that allows assessment of mental status (level of awareness and interaction with the environment); motor and sensory skills; balance and coordination. Today, more than 2000 genes have been discovered for normal brain function, the dysfunction of which can lead to

alteration of brain activity. This condition is enhanced in chromosomal diseases, when there is a (micro)deletion or (micro)duplication of a larger region of DNA where several genes are involved simultaneously. These disorders are neurogenetic developmental diseases characterized by intellectual disability, dysmorphic features, behavioral problems (autism, hyperactivity), neurological and/or psychiatric diseases, and various malformations. In these patients, the neurological evaluation is characterized by cognitive dysfunction with a degree of mental retardation; verbal abnormality as well as impaired visual-spatial abilities; and some degree of motor impairment. Previous neuroimaging studies have shown that various structural alterations of the central nervous system (CNS) in affected children are directly related to their cognitive dysfunction. In most of these conditions, epileptic seizures are also common features, appearing as typical and specific, or as non-specific and refractory. This paper presents case series of chromosomal disorders diagnosed by aCGH (array comparative genomic hybridization technique), including deletion of 14q11.2 and 16p11.2 chromosome, 10q26.3 microduplication, 10q11.22 deletion, 18p11.32p11.21 deletion, 10q22.2q23.1 microduplication, which, apart from the specific craniofacial dysmorphic characteristics and various malformations, are also characterized by significant neurological abnormalities. Regarding the neurological assessment, all five cases are characterized by cognitive impairment with a certain degree of mental retardation and motor developmental delay. Epileptic seizures occur in two cases, whereas, complex epileptic seizures, refractory and infantile spasms are characteristic of 14q11.2 and 16p11.2 deletion and atypical epileptic seizures characteristic of 10q22.2q23.1 microduplication. Other notable neurological impairments include severe hypotonia in 10q22.2q23.1 microduplication and 14q11.2 and 16p11.2 deletion, lack of concentration in 10q26.3 microduplication, impaired social skills in 10q11.22 deletion, speech abnormalities and abnormal gait in 18p11.32p11.21 deletion as well as febrile seizures. Regarding these characteristics, the treatment of chromosomal disorders should include periodic neurological evaluations and frequent clinical check-ups that also include recommendations for medical, speech, psychiatric and academic problems.

Keywords: chromosomal disorders, neurological assessment, seizures, developmental delay, mental retardation

MITOCHONDRIA – AS A TARGET OF ENVIRONMENTAL FACTORS

¹Tamar Giorgadze, ²Sofia Giorgadze

¹MD; PhD; Assistant Professor.

²MD; PhD; Associate Professor.

^{1,2}Department of Histology, Cytology and Embryology, Tbilisi State Medical University

ABSTRACT

Mitochondria—tiny organelles in the cell that each possess their own DNA—have come under a growing scientific spotlight. The traditional view of mitochondria as static organelles has been reassessed. Scientists increasingly believe they play a central role in many, if not most, human illnesses. Mitochondria are often target of toxicity of environmental toxicants resulting in multisystem disorders involving different cells, tissues, and organs.

The purpose of this review is to discuss the mechanism and consequences of mitochondrial dysfunction caused by environmental factors.

Recognition of the key role of mtDNA integrity and mitochondrial function in health has grown greatly in recent years. The environment can influence human health and disease in many harmful ways. One such mechanism for this is through environmental factors increasing oxidative stress in the cell, and this stress can subsequently lead to alterations in DNA molecule. Research shows that mitochondrial DNA is uniquely susceptible to the damaging effects of reactive oxygen species (ROS). These effects are more extensive and longer-lasting in mitochondrial DNA than they are in the nuclear genome. In humans, the most concerning chemicals may be mitochondrial toxins with long half-lives. Examples include lipophilic chemical mixtures such as persistent organic pollutants (POPs) and heavy metals. Other examples of chronic exposure to mitochondrial toxins are air pollution and cigarette smoking. Compared with its nuclear counterpart, mitochondrial DNA generally has less capacity to repair itself. It specifically can't delete the large DNA helix—

distorting adducts formed when mitochondrial DNA bases are damaged by mutagens such as polyaromatic hydrocarbons and ultraviolet radiation.

Conclusion - Despite numerous existing researches, the specified question requires further study. It is necessary clearer understanding of what specific environmental factors damage mitochondria and how they do so, this is important way to prevent many diseases induced by mitochondrial dysfunction.

Keywords: Mitochondria; Environmental Factors; Mitochondrial dysfunction.

SÜD VƏZİSİ XƏRÇƏNGİNDƏ AKSİLYAR LİMFODİSSEKSIYADAN SONRA LİMFOSTAZIN ƏMƏLƏGƏLMƏ AMİLLƏRİ

Quliyeva Tamara

Azərbaycan Tibb Universitetinin Onkologiya kafedrası.

Aktuallıq. Süd vəzisi xərçəngi ilə xəstələrin radikal müalicəsində cərrahi müdaxilə mütləq və əsas komponent hesab olunur. Əməliyyatdan sonrakı gecikmiş dövrdə müşahidə edilən yuxarı ətraflarda limfostaz və bununla bağlı yuxarı ətrafların funksiyasının məhdudlaşdırılması kimi fəsad xəstələrin həyat keyfiyyətini əhəmiyyətli dərəcədə aşağı salır.

İşin məqsədi. Süd vəzisi xərçəngi ilə xəstələrin cərrahi müdaxilədən sonra müşahidə olunan limfostazın əmələ gəlmə amillərinin müəyyənləşdirilməsi.

Material və metodlar. Tədqiqata 2019-2021-ci illər ərzində ATU-nun Onkoloji klinikasında müalicə olunmuş süd vəzisi xərçəngi ilə 350 xəstə daxil olmuşdur. Onlardan 183 xəstəyə orqanqoruyucu, 167 xəstəyə isə əməliyyat Maddən üsulu ilə radikal mastektomiya əməliyyatı icra edilmişdir. Bütün xəstələrə qoltuqaltı və körpücükaltı limfodisseksiya icra edilmişdir. Ehtimal baxımından limfodemanın əmələ gəlmə risk faktorlarına xəstələrin yaşı, bədən kütləsinin indeksi (BKİ), T və N göstəriciləri, şüa terapiyası, kimyəvi terapiya və əməliyyatın həcmi kimi amilləri nəzərdən keçirmişik. BKİ-ni mövcüd düsturlar – çəki (kq) / boy (sm) hesablanmışdır. Əməliyyat olunan tərəfdən yuxarı ətrafın məhdud funksiyası ilə əlaqədar xəstələrin həyati fəaliyyətinin pozulma dərəcəsi 100 ballıq DASH anketi ilə qiymətləndirilib. Statistik işləmə Statistica 10.0 kompüter proqramı ilə aparılmışdır.

Nəticələr. Müayinə zamanı xəstələrin 35,3% -ində bu və ya digər dərəcədə limfostaz inkişaf etmişdir. Ödem inkişafına xəstələrin yaşı, T və N göstəriciləri təsir etməmişdir. Statistik təhlillər göstərmişdir ki, şüa terapiyası ($p = 0,053$) və BKİ 25-dən yuxarı ($p = 0,061$) limfostazın inkişafında müstəqil proqnostik amil ola bilər. Aparılan biramilli dispersiya təhlili göstərmişdir ki, radikal mastektomiyadan sonra əməliyyat tərəfində yuxarı ətrafın məhdud hərəkətliyinə görə iş qabiliyyətinin azalması orqanqoruyucu əməliyyatlarla müqayisədə daha aydın görünür ($p = 0,074$).

Yekun. Xəstənin yüksək BKİ-si, əməliyyatdan sonrakı şüa terapiyası və radikal mastektomiya əməliyyat tərəfində yuxarı ətrafın limfostazının inkişaf riskini artırır, ətrafların funksiyasını məhdudlaşdırır və xəstələrin həyat keyfiyyətini azaldır. Süd vəzisi xərçəngi diaqnozu qoyulmuş xəstələrdə orqanqoruyucu əməliyyatlar limfostazın inkişafında statistik əhəmiyyətli azalma ilə nəticələnir.

Açar sözlər: Süd vəzisi xərçəngi, xəstələrin radikal müalicəsi.

ХАРАКТЕРИСТИКА ИММУННОГО СТАТУСА В ЭТАПЕ ВОЗРАСТНОЙ ИНВОЛЮЦИИ У ЛЮДЕЙ

^{1,2}Т.С. Абаева, ¹М.Т. Жанганаева, ²З.Тойчиева

¹Кыргызская государственная медицинская академия имени И.К.Ахунбаева, Бишкек, Кыргызстан,

²Ошский государственный университет, Ош, Кыргызстан.

РЕЗЮМЕ

С медико-биологической точки зрения, у человека различают несколько возрастных периодов. Эти периоды, переходящие без резких границ один в другой, характеризуются некоторыми особенностями. Инволютивные изменения в организме человека в первую очередь развиваются в органах, выполняющих наибольшую функциональную нагрузку при поддержании гомеостаза, и

характеризуются гетеротопностью, гетерохронностью, гетерокинетичностью, гетерокатефтенностью. При старении эффективность функционирования иммунной системы, заключающаяся в поддержании постоянства антигенного состава организма, уменьшается.

Целью настоящего исследования является изучение иммунного статуса на этапе возрастной инволюции у людей.

Материалы и методы исследования. Морфология иммунного статуса изучена от 22 людей пожилого и 24 старческого возраста у жителей г. Кара-Балта.

Для исследования брали периферическую венозную кровь (5-7 мл) из локтевой вены утром натощак. Для сравнения переменных с нормальным распределением использовался тест Стьюдента. Данные представлены как среднее стандартная ошибка ($M \pm m$). Статистическая значимость присваивалась при $P < 0,05$.

Результаты исследования и их обсуждение. В результате проведенного исследования, что иммунный статус у жителей пожилого возраста г. Кара-Балта установлено: 1. Субпопуляции лимфоцитов (РИФ) установлено, что Т- лимфоциты (CD3+) составляет $44,5 \pm 3,2$. В- лимфоциты (CD 19+) $23,8 \pm 0,9$, Т-хелперы (CD4+) $24,0 \pm 2,4$, Цитотоксические лимфоциты (CD8+) $11,3 \pm 1,3$. NK-клетки (CD 16+) $30,0 \pm 0,9$, ИРИ-2,2 $\pm 0,2$. 2. Гуморальное звено иммунитета. ЦИК, г/л $119,5 \pm 12,5$. 3. Макрофагально-фагоцитарное звено иммунитета. ФП (нейтрофилов) $39,8 \pm 0,3$. ФЧ (нейтрофилов) $1,7 \pm 0,07$ ИФИ (интегральный фагоцитарный индекс) $0,64 \pm 0,05$.

В результате проведенного исследования, что иммунный статус у жителей старческого возраста г. Кара-Балта установлено, что показатели уменьшились: 1. Субпопуляции лимфоцитов (РИФ) установлено, что Т- лимфоциты (CD3+) на 14,6%. Т-хелперы (CD4+) на 20,8%. Цитотоксические лимфоциты (CD8+) -на 29,2%. 2. Гуморальное звено иммунитета. ЦИК, г/л на 16,3%. 3. Макрофагально-фагоцитарное звено иммунитета. ФП (нейтрофилов) 4,5%. ФЧ (нейтрофилов) на 11,7%. ИФИ (интегральный фагоцитарный индекс) на 10,5%. Почти одинаковые показатели В- лимфоциты (CD 19+) $23,5 \pm 1,5$. ИРИ-2,2 $\pm 0,09$. В старческом возрасте показатель NK-клетки (CD 16+) немного увеличен и составляет 3,3 %.

Заключение. Таким образом, Проведенные исследования показали наличие закономерных возрастных изменений в результате анализов иммунного статуса и субпопуляции лимфоцитов у людей пожилого и старческого возраста все показатели уменьшены от нормы, В лимфоциты в пределах нормы, а показатель NK-клетки (CD 16+) немного увеличен (3,3%). Проживание в г. Кара-Балта, расположенного вблизи уранового хвостохранилища сопровождаются нарушением кроветворной функции костного мозга и изменениями клеточного состава, соответствующие различной степени патологических процессов.

Ключевые слова: функции костного мозга, Инволютивные изменения в организме человека.

КОРРЕЛЯЦИЯ МЕЖДУ КАЧЕСТВОМ ЖИЗНИ И ТЯЖЕСТЬЮ ЗАБОЛЕВАНИЯ ПЕДИАТРИЧЕСКИХ ПАЦИЕНТОВ С АТОПИЧЕСКИМ ДЕРМАТИТОМ

¹Л.И.Аллахвердиева, ²Н.М.Гулиева, ³З.У.Мамедова

¹Проф., ²доц., ³PhD student

^{1,2,3}Азербайджанский Медицинский Университет, кафедра "Аллергологии и иммунологии", Баку, Азербайджан.

Введение. Атопический дерматит (АД) - одно из наиболее распространенных хронических рецидивирующих воспалительных заболеваний кожи со сложным патогенезом. Эта патология поражает в среднем 20% детского и 3% взрослого населения. Есть несколько патогенетических механизмов развития данного процесса.

Цель исследования. Оценить корреляцию между КЖ и тяжестью заболевания больных детей с атопическим дерматитом.

Материалы и методы. Исследование представляет собой наблюдательное аналитическое исследование, проведенное в детской клинической больнице №6 города Баку, в течение года. Всего в исследование были включены 34 пациента в возрасте от 0 до 16 лет. Критерии

включения были следующими: возраст от 3 месяцев до 16 лет и наличие поражений кожи, типичных для АД. Основным диагностическим критерием является зуд.

Результаты. В исследование были включены 34 пациента в возрасте от 0 до 16 лет.

Пациенты были разделены на 3 разные возрастные группы: 0-4 года (со средним возрастом 1,9 года), 5-9 лет (со средним возрастом 7,0 лет) и 10-16 лет (со средним возрастом 13,1 лет). В группе от 3 месяцев до 4 лет преобладающим полом был мужской, что составляет 70,3%, а женский - 29,7%. В следующих двух возрастных группах соотношение женщин и мужчин составляло 40/60%. Ассоциация сопутствующих аллергических заболеваний у детей из групп 5-9 и 10-16 лет встречалась чаще, чем в младшей возрастной группе.

Ключевые слова: атопический дерматит, качество жизни, SCORAD, IDQoL, CDQoL

CLINICAL AND DIAGNOSTIC FEATURES OF POSTMENOPAUSAL OSTEOPOROSIS IN WOMEN IN BAKU CITY

Shafaq Asadova, Sharifa Vagabova, Rena Gurbanova, Farida Abbasova, Shafa Amiraslanova

^{1,2,3,4,5}Azerbaijan Medical University, Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology

¹Candidate of Medical Sciences, Associate Professor,

²Doctor of Philosophy in Medicine, assistant,

³Candidate of Medical Sciences, Associate Professor,

⁴Candidate of Medical Sciences, Associate Professor,

⁵Doctor of Philosophy in Medicine, assistant.

ABSTRACT

This article is devoted to the examination and treatment of 72 sick women with postmenopausal osteoporosis aged 40–65 years. The identification of patients with postmenopausal osteoporosis was carried out on the basis of data obtained during a preliminary examination using clinical and paraclinical examination methods. The diagnosis of osteoporosis was carried out according to X-ray examination using a DEXXUM 3 bone densitometer, using DEXA technology, which combines a number of advantages, allowing with the highest accuracy to determine the mineral density of bone tissue, the content of bone minerals to determine the fragility of bones and the likelihood of fractures. The presented results of therapy and prevention of postmenopausal osteoporosis in women, residents of Baku, indicate the need to organize specialized gynecological offices in antenatal clinics, general clinics, for dispensary observation of women in the menopausal period, which will help reduce the incidence of postmenopausal osteoporosis in women in transition age.

Keywords: dispensary observation, antenatal clinics, general clinics.

THE MANIFESTATION OF SOME KEY ISSUE ASPECTS OF PECULIARITIES OF ENDOVASCULAR SURGERY BASED ON ENDOVASCULAR EMBOLIZATION FOR BLEEDING FROM GASTRO-DUODENAL ULCER AND FEATURES OF SOME ESSENTIAL PHARMACOTHERAPY

Gocha Chankseliani¹, Avtandil Girdaladze¹, Omar Gibradze², Paata Meshveliani²,

Kakha Chelidze³, Mirian Cheishvili³, Ana Kvernadze³, Nodar Sulashvili⁴

¹Tbilisi State University; Faculty of Medicine; ²Akaki Tsereteli State University, Faculty of Medicine,

³Multiprofile-Clinic «L&J», ⁴Tbilisi State Medical University.

ABSTRACT

Aim of the research was to study the key issue aspects of peculiarities of endovascular surgery and endovascular embolization for bleeding from gastro-duodenal ulcer. Gastrointestinal bleedings (GIBs) are

pathological conditions associated with significant morbidity and mortality. Embolization without angiographic evidence of contrast media extravasation is proposed as an effective procedure in patients with clinical and/or laboratory signs of bleeding. The purpose of this systematic review is to define common clinical practice and clinical and technical outcomes of blind and preventive embolization for upper and lower gastrointestinal bleeding. Knowledge of vascular anatomy is essential to achieve adequate hemostasis. Endovascular embolization dramatically reduces the mortality rate in high-risk patients who require open surgery after failed endoscopy, further studies are needed to fully address these objectives. Endovascular therapy for upper and lower gastrointestinal bleeding is a minimally invasive procedure that should be performed according to guidelines and with close interdisciplinary collaboration. The underlying etiology of bleeding, the location and dynamics of bleeding, as well as the structural, personnel, and equipment conditions of the relevant site, are all factors that influence the choice of diagnostic and therapeutic measures. Previous data indicate that endovascular strategies may be beneficial for morbidity and mortality in patients at high surgical risk. Embolization is a safe procedure in patients with non-variceal UGI bleeding, and the complication rate is very low and most often transient with treatment. Complications described include access site complications, target vessel resection, hepatic or splenic infarction, and duodenal stenosis. Several cases of intestinal ischemia and necrosis after embolization have also been described. Gastrointestinal (GI) bleeding is a relatively common condition with a wide range of underlying causes. In most cases, this acute bleeding is effectively managed by conservative, medical or endoscopic procedures. However, the proportion of endoscopically unrecognized or controlled non-variceal gastrointestinal bleeding still requires alternative, sometimes surgical, treatment. The current guideline "Gastrointestinal Bleeding" gives importance to interventional radiology in considering its minimally invasive endovascular interdisciplinary therapy options, guideline-oriented endovascular treatment of GI bleeding by embolization and implantation of covered stents is a treatment approach with good technical and clinical success rates and low complication rates. Knowledge of vascular anatomy is essential to achieve adequate hemostasis. Endovascular embolization dramatically reduces the mortality rate in high-risk patients who require open surgery after failed endoscopy, further studies are needed to fully address these objectives. Typically, endovascular treatment of upper gastrointestinal or lower gastrointestinal bleeding is performed under local anesthesia via a transfemoral access route, although a trans brachial approach may also be considered, especially in the case of an unfavorable angle of descent of the visceral vessels. Endovascular therapy for upper and lower gastrointestinal bleeding is a minimally invasive procedure that should be performed according to guidelines and with close interdisciplinary collaboration. The underlying etiology of bleeding, the location and dynamics of bleeding, as well as the structural, personnel, and equipment conditions of the relevant site, are all factors that influence the choice of diagnostic and therapeutic measures. Previous data indicate that endovascular strategies may be beneficial for morbidity and mortality in patients at high surgical risk.

Keywords: Manifestation, peculiarities, endovascular surgery, duodenal ulcer bleeding.

THE MANIFESTATION OF KEY ISSUE ASPECTS OF FEATURES OF THE EFFECTS OF CISPLATIN IN VARIOUS CLINICAL APPLICATIONS AND SAFETY CHALLENGES

Nodar Sulashvili¹, Luiza Gabunia², Nana Gorgaslidze³, Nato Alavidze⁴, Ketevan Chakhnashvili⁵, Tamar Okropiridze⁶, Igor Seniuk⁷

^{1,2,3}MD, PhD, Tbilisi State Medical University, Tbilisi, Georgia,

⁴MD, PhD, Akaki Tsereteli State University, Tbilisi, Georgia,

⁵MD, PhD, Professor, International Medical School at Alte University; Tbilisi, Georgia,

⁶MD, PhD, Doctor Medical Sciences, International School of Medicine at Alte University, Tbilisi, Georgia,

⁷MD, PhD, National University of Pharmacy, Vice Dean, Kharkiv, Ukraine.

ABSTRACT

Aim of the research was to study the features of the effects of cisplatin in various clinical applications and safety challenges. Cisplatin and other platinum-based drugs, such as carboplatin, ormaplatin, and oxaliplatin, have been widely used to treat a multitude of human cancers. However, a considerable proportion of patients often relapse due to drug resistance and/or toxicity to multiple organs including the liver, kidneys, gastrointestinal tract, and the cardiovascular, hematologic, and nervous systems. Cisplatin use of in cancer

therapy, with a special emphasis on its molecular mechanisms of action and treatment modalities including the combination therapy with natural products. Even though promising new treatment approaches have been implemented, cancer is still undefeated. Research has shown that certain risk factors are associated with the development of cancer, causing substantial morbidity and mortality rates. Some of the associated risk factors for the development of cancer include age, alcohol consumption, carcinogenic substances, chronic inflammation, diet, genetic mutations, hormones, immunosuppression, infectious agents, obesity, radiation, sunlight exposure and tobacco usage. Cisplatin is one of the most effective chemotherapy drugs, widely used in the treatment of solid tumors. It is widely used to treat various types of tumors, including head and neck, lung, ovarian, leukemia, breast, brain, kidney and testicular cancers. Cisplatin and other platinum compounds are generally considered cytotoxic drugs that kill cancer cells by damaging DNA, inhibiting DNA synthesis and mitosis, and causing cell death through apoptosis. Several molecular mechanisms, including induction of oxidative stress characterized by the production of reactive oxygen species and lipid peroxidation, induction of p53 signaling and cell cycle arrest, suppression of pro-oncogenes and anti-apoptotic proteins, and activation of intrinsic and extrinsic factors, leading to apoptosis.

Keywords: Features, cisplatin, effects, various, clinical, applications, side effect.

ENDOTHELIAL GLYCOCALYX DAMAGE IN PATIENTS WITH SEVERE FUNCTIONAL INJURY

Sarkulova Zh. N., Tokshilykova A.B., Sarkulov M.N., Daniyarova K.R., Kalieva B.M., Zhankulov M.H.
Marat Ospanov West Kazakhstan Medical University, Kazakhstan

In modern medical science, endothelial glycocalyx, which is considered a target organ in many diseases, including severe traumatic injuries, is becoming one of the main objects of researchers' attention. Trauma is the leading cause of death and disability worldwide, and despite the introduction of damage-controlled resuscitation, mortality remains very high. More than half of trauma patients are found to have laboratory-defined coagulopathy on admission, which further leads to increased mortality. Laboratory-defined coagulopathy, also called trauma-induced coagulopathy, is described as either excessive activation of the protein C pathway accompanied by hyperfibrinolysis or as a manifestation of the hemorrhagic phenotype of disseminated intravascular coagulation. Common to both of these explanations is that, they are based on the measurement of concentrations of pro- and anticoagulant clotting factors, platelet counts, and fibrin degradation products.

The cause of severe combined trauma was road traffic accidents in 41 cases (68.3%), various other traumas, including stabbings and falls, in 12 cases (20.1%), and industrial trauma in 7 cases (11.6%).

Thromboelastographic study of whole citrate blood was performed at three different stages - on the 1st, 3rd and 7th day from the patient's admission to the intensive care unit.

Results and discussion. During the study of fibrinolytic activity of whole blood samples in victims with severe combined traumas the increase of LY30, LY60 levels and decrease of CL30 and CL60 indices were determined.

Materials and research methods. The studied patients were aged from 19 to 78 years; thus the mean age was 47 ± 9.1 years. Among them 37 (62.7%) were males and 23 (38.3%) were females.

Conclusion. 1. Thromboelastogram with cellular model of blood coagulation allows timely diagnosis of trauma-associated coagulopathy.

2. Based on the obtained data, it can be stated that in the evaluation of TEG results, the decrease in amplitude is due to the activation of fibrinolytic processes in the hemostasis system in patients with severe combined traumas.

3. The revealed traumatic coagulopathy may reflect the damage of endothelial glycocalyx in patients with severe functional injuries in traumas.

THE KEY ISSUES ASPECTS OF MANIFESTATION OF PECULIARITIES AND CHARACTERISTICS OF TREHALOSE-BINDING SOLUBLE LECTIN OBTAINED FROM MENTHA PULEGIUM

Madona Chachua¹, Nodar Sulashvili², Nana Gorgaslidze³, Nato Alavidze⁴, Tamar Okropiridze⁵, Igor Seniuk⁶

¹PhD, Doctor of Biological Sciences, Professor of Biochemistry of Faculty of Medicine at Teaching National University SEU, Tbilisi, Georgia.

²MD, PhD, Doctor of Pharmaceutical and Pharmacological Sciences, Invited Lecturer of Scientific Research-Skills Center at Tbilisi State Medical University, Tbilisi, Georgia.

³MD, PhD, Doctor of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Professor of Tbilisi State Medical University, Tbilisi, Georgia.

⁴MD, PhD, Doctor of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Professor of Akaki Tsereteli State University, Faculty of Medicine, Department of Pharmacy, Kutaisi, Georgia.

⁵MD, PhD, Doctor Medical Sciences, Professor of the Division of Dentistry of International School of Medicine at Alte University, Tbilisi, Georgia.

⁶MD, PhD, Doctor of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Associate Professor of Biological Chemistry Department at National University of Pharmacy, Kharkiv, Ukraine.

ABSTRACT

Trehalose-binding soluble lectin from *Mentha pulegium* was purified by affinity chromatography on trypsin-treated glutaraldehyde-fixed rabbit erythrocyte column. Hemagglutination activity of the lectine occurs in a relatively broad range of pH (pH 6.5-9.0) and is characterized by a strongly marked optimum (pH 7.5). The lectin is a thermally stable protein and maintains its activity after its incubation at 70°C during 10 min. Soluble lectins selectively suppress the growth and development of *Actinomyces griseus* and *Streptomyces albobrisesolus* subsp. *aragviensis*. In their presence the viability of *Streptomyces albobrisesolus* subsp. *aragviensis* spores depending on concentration decreases notably. So, after the purification of the *Mentha pulegium* soluble lectin fraction by affinity chromatography and gel-filtration two protein fractions with different lectin activity and sugar specificity were revealed: first galacturonic acid binding (67 kDa) and second trehalose binding (20 kDa) – MPTL. For MPTL activity the existence of divalent ions (Ca²⁺, Mg²⁺) is not necessary. MPTL activity is maximum at pH 7.5 and is unaffected by heat treatment up to 70°C for 10 min. It was shown by hemagglutination test that both first and second peaks agglutinate trypsin treated rabbit erythrocytes. Hapten-inhibitory experiments detected that the first peak is D-galacturonic acid binding as its hemagglutination activity was inhibited by D-galacturonic acid (25 mM) and only D-trehalose-dihydrate gave inhibition of the second peak hemagglutination activity at sugar concentration of 6.0 mM. Thus, the second peak shows trehalose-binding property and it was named MPTL (*Mentha pulegium* trehalose-binding lectin). Above-mentioned proteins have also different molecular weights (Fig. 2). The molecular weight of D-galacturonic acid binding lectin is 67 000 and that of the MPTL is 20 000. Lectin molecules frequently contain non-protein components such as metal ions Ca²⁺, Mg²⁺, seldom - Mn²⁺, Zn²⁺, etc. Metal ions are bonded with several amino acid residues and therefore lead to the stabilization of lectin structure. They play a considerable part in revealing lectin biological properties.

Keywords: Lectin, obtained, *Mentha Pulegium*, trehalose-binding lectin, hemagglutination activity.

THE MANIFESTATION OF FEATURES OF DRIVING FORCES FOR BENEFICIAL AND WHOLESOME THEORIES FOR PHARMACEUTICAL INSTITUTIONS CHALLENGES WORLDWIDE AND THE ENTITY OF SIGNIFICANCE OF CONDUCTING

Nana Gorgaslidze¹, Nodar Sulashvili²

¹MD, PhD, Doctor of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Professor of Tbilisi State Medical University, Tbilisi, Georgia.

²MD, PhD, Doctor of Pharmaceutical and Pharmacological Sciences, Invited Lecturer of Scientific Research-Skills Center at Tbilisi State Medical University, Tbilisi, Georgia.

ABSTRACT

Aim of the research was to study features of driving forces for beneficial and wholesome theories for pharmaceutical institutions challenges worldwide and the entity of significance of conducting. The activities of pharmaceutical institutions require a style of work that is based on the constant search for new opportunities, the ability to attract and use resources from various sources to solve problems, thereby increasing production efficiency. In such conditions, the requirements for organizational management and management increase. The manager must ensure the organization of the enterprise's activities to meet market demand; he must have a constant desire to increase production efficiency, make reasonable and optimal decisions and control it. The term "management" is not interpreted as management in a broad sense, but as leadership, management, business organization, especially its economic management. Management can be considered as a system of knowledge about production and service, organization, methods, techniques and technology, patterns of development of human relations. Human resources are an invaluable asset for any business, including pharmaceutical institutions. Human resource is a potential that, if properly managed, will turn into an invaluable intangible asset for a company. The success of a company is impossible without human resources managers, who attach great importance to the approach to employees and their motivation. Therefore, the manager's responsibility to his employees is to carefully monitor them and find out in time what active needs each of them has. In our opinion, based on this, the manager must make a decision on their implementation, which will help improve work efficiency. Every organization should have a training program that will enhance the capabilities of staff and help them cope with new challenges, such as new equipment and techniques. Social security is a means of increasing motivation - this can be health insurance, gifts for the holidays, memberships in sports and recreational institutions, etc. Even minimal social security motivates employees, because a person has a sense of stability, which encourages him to work conscientiously. To create a motivated team, it is necessary to have access to information and communication: communication involves the exchange of information, which is a necessary condition for the effective functioning of organizations. If each employee is not provided with enough information and if he himself suffers from a lack of information and communication, his productivity is expected to decline, so managers must ensure their motivation by providing sufficient, relevant and necessary information. This is a list of the main factors that have the most important influence on work motivation, although managers may also use different motivators depending on specific situations.

Keywords: Features, driving forces, beneficial, wholesome, theories, pharmaceutical, institutions, challenges, worldwide.

THE MANIFESTATION OF PECULIARITIES OF PHARMACOLOGICAL EFFECTS OF THE MEDICINAL PRODUCT – “PHENOMENON” ON LIVER BIOCHEMICAL AND FUNCTIONALITY OPTIONS RESULTS, IN CCL4- PROVOKED TENTATIVE LIVER CIRRHOSIS ON LAB RATS

Luiza Gabunia¹, Ketevan Ghambashidze², Levan Ratiani³, Nodar Sulashvili⁴, Nana Gorgaslidze⁵, Lia Gumbaridze⁶, Gigi Gorgadze⁷, Buka Bendeliani⁸, Nino Chumburidze-Areshidze⁹

¹MD, PhD, Doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor, Director of the Scientific Research-Skills Center at Tbilisi State Medical University, Tbilisi, Georgia,

²MD, PhD, Doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor of Department of Pathological Physiology at Tbilisi State Medical University, Tbilisi, Georgia,

³MD, PhD, Doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor, General Director of the First University Clinic of Tbilisi State Medical University,

⁴MD, PhD, Doctor of Pharmaceutical and Pharmacological Sciences, Invited Lecturer of Scientific Research-Skills Center at Tbilisi State Medical University, Tbilisi, Georgia,

⁵MD, PhD, Doctor of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Professor of Tbilisi State Medical University, Tbilisi, Georgia.

⁶PhD, Doctor of Public Health, Invited Lecturer of Scientific Research-Skills Center at Tbilisi State Medical University, Tbilisi, Georgia,

⁷MD, Student of Faculty of Medicine at Tbilisi State Medical University, Tbilisi, Georgia,

⁸MD Student of Faculty of Medicine at Tbilisi State Medical University, Scientific Research-Skills Center at Tbilisi State Medical University, Tbilisi, Georgia,

⁹Honorary Doctor of Tbilisi State Medical University, Deputy of General Director of the Tbilisi Central Hospital, Tbilisi, Georgia.

ABSTRACT

Aim of the research was to study peculiarities of pharmacological effects of the medicinal product – “Phenomenon” on liver biochemical and functionality options results, in CCL4- provoked tentative liver cirrhosis on lab rats. Cirrhosis is a pathological consequence of a number of chronic liver diseases, and fibrosis is a precursor to cirrhosis. Various cell types, cytokines and microRNAs are involved in the development and progression of liver fibrosis and cirrhosis. Activation of hepatic stellate cells (HSCs) is a key event in fibrosis. Liver endothelial cell protection and capillary formation are major factors contributing to liver dysfunction in cirrhosis. Activated cells destroy hepatocytes and stimulate hepatic stellate cells activation. Repeated cycles of cell death and hepatocyte regeneration contribute to the pathogenesis of liver cirrhosis. At the molecular level, many cytokines are involved in signaling pathways that regulate hepatic stellate cells activation and fibrogenesis. Liver cirrhosis is a chronic and progressive disease, a global health concern, with a high prevalence worldwide. We were aimed to investigate the treatment effects of the drug “Phenomenon” and S-ademethionine in case of CCl4-induced liver cirrhosis. Experiments were carried out on 200-250 g white laboratory rats. 0.1 ml of CCl4 was injected intraperitoneally twice a week during month for disease modeling. S-ademethionine (5 mg/kg) was injected intraperitoneally once a day. Phenomenon (12 mg/kg) was administered orally once a day, and Phenomenon diluted in 1.5 ml of honey was administered orally once a day during 20 days. Treatment efficacy was evaluated according to the biochemical parameters: Aspartate aminotransferase (AST), Alanine aminotransferase (ALT), Sodium phosphatase (ALP), Total bilirubin (TBIL), Cholesterol, serum Creatinine (CREA), Blood glucose, superoxide dismutase (SOD) and morphology of liver tissue. The investigations showed that in the control group AST, ALT, ALP, TBIL, cholesterol and triglycerides were significantly increased while, creatinine and SOD were decreased compared to the data of healthy rats. Massive necrosis of hepatocytes and accompanied inflammatory processes impaired functions of the liver. The detoxification functions, metabolism of cholesterol, bilirubin and triglycerides were disordered, protein synthesis decreased, glycogen synthesis was inhibited, and blood glucose was increased. The better therapeutic effects were detected at treatment with Phenomenon, especially at combination Phenomenon+honey compared to the data of the animals treated with S-ademethionine. Phenomenon reveals antioxidant, membrane-stabilizing, hepatoprotective properties, decreases lipid peroxidation, inhibits damage of hepatocytes, and improves liver functions in CCl4 induced liver cirrhosis in lab rats. ALT is an enzyme found predominantly in hepatocytes (lower concentrations in heart, kidney, and muscle tissue) and is therefore specific for hepatocellular injury. ALT levels often fluctuate throughout the day. ALT promotes the formation of glutamate and pyruvate in hepatocytes, which are important for energy production. AST is an enzyme that, like ALT, is also found in the liver, but there are other places where it is not as abundant as ALT. These sites are mainly skeletal muscle, cardiac muscle, kidney tissue and the brain. These are two isoenzymes that cannot be distinguished by standard tests and have little clinical value. AST facilitates amino acid metabolism. Regarding AST, caution should be used when assessing abnormal levels because it is present in other tissues.

Keywords: Pharmacological, effects, medicinal, product, – “Phenomenon” liver biochemical, functionality, results, liver, cirrhosis.

THE MANIFESTATION OF PECULIARITIES OF TEMOZOLOMIDE MECHANISM OF ACTION, SOME PHARMACOTHERAPEUTIC EFFECTS AND RESISTANCE MECHANISMS IN CANCER IN CLINICAL APPLICATIONS

Nodar Sulashvili¹, Luiza Gabunia², Nana Gorgaslidze³, Levan Ratiani⁴, Ketevan Ghambashidze⁵, Nato Alavidze⁶, Marina Giorgobiani⁷, Tamar Okropiridze⁸

¹MD, PhD, Doctor of Pharmaceutical and Pharmacological Sciences, Invited Lecturer of Scientific Research-Skills Center at Tbilisi State Medical University, Tbilisi, Georgia,

²MD, PhD, Doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor, Director of the Scientific Research-Skills Center at Tbilisi State Medical University, Tbilisi, Georgia,

³MD, PhD, Doctor of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Professor of Tbilisi State Medical University, Tbilisi, Georgia.

⁴MD, PhD, Doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor, General Director of the First University Clinic of Tbilisi State Medical University, Head of the Department of Emergency Medicine, Reanimatology and Anesthesiology at Tbilisi State Medical University, Tbilisi, Georgia,

⁵MD, PhD, Doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor of Department of Pathological Physiology at Tbilisi State Medical University, Tbilisi, Georgia,

⁶MD, PhD, Doctor of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Professor of Akaki Tsereteli State University, Faculty of Medicine, Department of Pharmacy, Kutaisi, Georgia.

⁷MD, PhD, Doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor of Tbilisi State Medical University, Department of Hygiene and Medical Ecology, Tbilisi, Georgia.

⁸MD, PhD, Doctor Medical Sciences, Professor of the Division of Dentistry of International School of Medicine at Alte University, Tbilisi, Georgia.

ABSTRACT

Aim of the research was to study and analyse the manifestation of peculiarities of temozolomide mechanism of action, some pharmacotherapeutic effects and resistance mechanisms in cancer in clinical applications. Glioblastoma multiforme (GBM) is a malignant brain tumor that arises from the glial cells of intracranial tissue. GBM invades surrounding tissue and reduces neurological function, resulting in poor quality of life for patients. Temozolomide is the most commonly used chemotherapy drug in patients with glioblastoma, although about half of those treated are resistant to temozolomide, and some patients eventually fail. Due to the limited effectiveness of existing therapies, immunotherapy in patients with glioblastoma is under intense investigation. However, early attempts at immunotherapy in glioblastoma patients as monotherapy have had disappointing results. Therefore, combinatorial treatment strategies are being explored. Temozolomide has multiple effects on the immune system that depend on the route of administration and dosing strategy and may have unpredictable consequences for immunotherapy. Temozolomide has both direct antitumor activity and immunomodulatory properties. The timing and dose of temozolomide significantly alters its effects on immune cells and the tumor microenvironment. The specific cytotoxic activity of Temozolomide (TMZ) is based on active cell proliferation and rapid DNA replication. As previously mentioned, proliferating cells that lack adequate MMR repair will ultimately lead to an increase in mutations in response to TMZ treatment. Slower proliferation could protect against the development of a hypermutated relapse phenotype; However, this could also reduce the effectiveness of TMZ-specific killing of tumor cells. By increasing the number of mutations and the potential for genetic diversity within a tumor, TMZ treatment may limit the effectiveness of antigen-targeted immunotherapies such as DC vaccines and CAR-T cells. Therefore, it is important the studies evaluate the effects of TMZ dose timing after radiation treatment to establish a beneficial balance between tumor cell proliferation and quiescence. Temozolomide (TMZ) is the most commonly used chemotherapy drug in GBM. However, in some patients, resistance is associated with mutations in isocitrate dehydrogenase 1 (IDH1) and high levels of MGMT (O6-methylguanine-DNA methyltransferase) promoter methylation, resulting in reduced efficacy of standard treatment with TMZ. TMZ treatment has been shown to directly target tumor cells and exhibit reasonable toxicity at high doses. In studies designed to increase the effect of chemotherapy in a patient, higher doses were used for short periods of time and lower doses continuously. Different doses of TMZ can alter DNA repair mechanisms and the overall genetic profile of the tumor, as well as the composition of the immune cells surrounding the tumor. Brain tumors differ from others by several factors, including the isolation of tumors beyond the blood-brain barrier, the general genetic heterogeneity and invasiveness of GBM, and the combined immunosuppression of the brain environment and the tumor itself. the standard treatment of used in patients to reduce tumor burden by directly killing proliferating tumor cells. The drug can also cause mutations in surviving tumor cells and kill some proliferating immune cells, which may limit the effectiveness of current immunotherapy strategies.

Keywords: Temozolomide, mechanism, action, pharmacotherapeutic effects, resistance mechanisms, cancer, clinical.

THE MANIFESTATION OF PECULIARITIES, SIDE EFFECTS AND TOXICITIES OF DRUGS AND THEIR SUMMONS FEATURES IN CLINICAL APPLICATION AT DIFFERENT AGES

Nana Gorgaslidze¹, Shafiga Topchiyeva², Nodar Sulashvili³

¹MD, PhD, Doctor of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Professor of Tbilisi State Medical University, Tbilisi, Georgia.

²PhD, Doctor of Biological Sciences, Professor of Institute of Zoology, National Academy of Sciences of Azerbaijan, Baku, Azerbaijan.

³MD, PhD, Doctor of Pharmaceutical and Pharmacological Sciences, Invited Lecturer of Scientific Research-Skills Center at Tbilisi State Medical University, Tbilisi, Georgia.

ABSTRACT

The aim of the research was to study the peculiarities, side effects and toxicities of drugs and their summons features in clinical application at different ages. The goal of drug therapy is to prolong life and improve sensitivity in elderly patients. Prescribing medications to elderly patients should be based on the following principles: To clarify the diagnosis, whether it is necessary to prescribe the drug. The form of the drug should be chosen carefully and correctly. In most cases, treatment should be started with a low dose and increased until the desired effect is achieved. It is necessary to carefully collect a medical history, including drug interactions. If the patient takes any medications (herbal) regardless of the doctor. Analyzing new symptoms used during treatment and focusing on side effects. Simplification of the dosing regimen. Accuracy of the administration regimen during simultaneous administration of several drugs. Reasoned exclusion of the prescribed drug from the treatment regimen. Allergic reactions are the most common complication of drug treatment. They are based on immunological mechanisms. Antibodies are formed in response to a drug, or more often its complex with a protein, when it is first introduced into the body. When the drug is reintroduced into the body, a drug-antigen reaction occurs with the resulting antibodies, degranulation of the cell membrane and the release of allergy mediators into the blood occurs, skin rash, Quincke's edema, serum sickness, anaphylactic reaction (immediate type) or organs (hepatitis in the liver, kidneys - glomerulonephritis, in the myocardium - myocarditis, etc.) necrotic focal rash (delayed type reaction). Such complications can be caused by antibiotics, sulfa drugs, non-narcotic analgesics, vitamin preparations, aminazine, and local anesthetics. The experiment revealed that there is a certain relationship between the amount of medication taken and the frequency of side effects. In geriatric practice, side effects of drugs are observed twice as often as in younger patients. In many cases, medical error caused by ignoring the side effects of the drug is due to underestimation of age-related changes; in the pharmacokinetic analysis of the drug, it is known that older people are characterized by a decrease in body weight (decrease in the amount of water in the body). volume and muscle mass), which reduces the distribution of the drug in the body, reduces the metabolic functions of the liver, reduces the degree of binding of blood to plasma proteins, blood supply to vital organs, homeostatic mechanisms weaken, the level of the disease increases, which leads to the prescription of drugs of various pharmacological groups. Taking into account the age aspect, the drug is prescribed in small doses to elderly patients. In recent years, the arsenal of drugs used in pediatric practice has significantly increased and enriched. However, the pediatrician must rationally assess both the benefits and risks of drug treatment. Unfortunately, all medications have side effects that often mimic another disease or appear as another disease, requiring additional medications. Children often experience side effects that are not seen in adults. It is necessary to take into account the neuropsychic status of the child, since children react differently to pain, to the bitter taste of the drug, and are more prone to allergic reactions. Therefore, the pediatrician must know the aspects of the development of pharmacological effects at different ages, the specifics of pharmacodynamics and pharmacokinetics of drugs in childhood, and possible complications of pharmacotherapy in a growing organism. That is, the reaction of the child's body to medications is due to the insufficiency of many systems that are simultaneously in the maturation stage.

Keywords: Peculiarities, side effect, toxicities drugs, features, clinical, application, different ages.

THE SCIENTIFIC TALKS OF CHARACTERISTICS OF SOME KEY ISSUE ASPECTS OF PHARMACISTS' PROFESSION, VOCATIONAL ACHIEVEMENTS, ENHANCEMENT, CHALLENGES, INCLINATION AND PERSPECTIVES IN PHARMACEUTICS AND MEDICINE BASED ON THE SUNLIGHT OF SOCIAL PHARMACY AT LOCAL AND GLOBAL LEVEL IN GENERAL

Nodar Sulashvili¹, Shafiga Topchiyeva², Vira Kravchenko³, Diego Rada Fernandez de Jauregui⁴, Luiza Gabunia⁵, Nana Gorgaslidze⁶, Tamar Tsintsadze⁷, Nino Abuladze⁸, Irine Pkhakadze⁹, Ketevani Gabunia¹⁰, Giorgi Pkhakadze¹¹, Nato Alavidze¹², Irine Zarnadze¹³, Natia Kvizhinadze¹⁴, Lela Grigolia¹⁵, Kakhaber Robakidze¹⁶, Marina Giorgobiani¹⁷, Shalva (Davit) Zarnadze¹⁸, Tamar Okropiridze¹⁹, Igor Seniuk²⁰

¹MD, PhD, Doctor of Pharmaceutical and Pharmacological Sciences, Invited Lecturer of Scientific Research-Skills Center at Tbilisi State Medical University, Tbilisi, Georgia,

²PhD, Doctor of Biological Sciences, Professor of Institute of Zoology, National Academy of Sciences of Azerbaijan, Baku, Azerbaijan,

³MD, PhD, Doctor of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Associate Professor of Biological Chemistry Department at National University of Pharmacy, Kharkiv, Ukraine.

⁴PhD and BSc in Pharmacy, MSc in Research Methodology in Health Sciences, Professor, Pharmacy Faculty, University of the Basque Country, Spain,

⁵MD, PhD, Doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor, Director of the Scientific Research-Skills Center at Tbilisi State Medical University, Tbilisi, Georgia,

⁶MD, PhD, Doctor of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Professor of Tbilisi State Medical University, Tbilisi, Georgia.

⁷MD, PhD, Doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor of Georgian Technical University, Tbilisi, Georgia.

⁸MD, PhD, Doctor of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Professor of Akaki Tsereteli State University, Faculty of Medicine, Department of Pharmacy, Kutaisi, Georgia,

⁹MD, PhD, Doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor of Akaki Tsereteli State University, Kutaisi, Georgia.

¹⁰MD, PhD, Doctor of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Professor of Akaki Tsereteli State University, Faculty of Medicine, Department of Pharmacy, Kutaisi, Georgia,

¹¹MD, MPH, PhD, Doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor, School of Public Health at David Tvildiani Medical University, Tbilisi, Georgia,

¹²MD, PhD, Doctor of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Professor of Akaki Tsereteli State University, Faculty of Medicine, Department of Pharmacy, Kutaisi, Georgia,

¹³MD, PhD, Doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor of Tbilisi State Medical University, Department of Public Health, Health Care Management, Policy and Economy, Tbilisi, Georgia,

¹⁴MD, PhD, Doctor of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Professor of Tbilisi State Medical University, Department of Social and Clinical Pharmacy. Tbilisi, Georgia,

¹⁵MD, PhD, Doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor of The Department of Dentistry at Caucasus International University; Tbilisi, Georgia,

¹⁶MD, PhD, Doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor of The Department of Dentistry at Caucasus International University; National Health Center named after Academician O. Gudushauri; Tbilisi, Georgia,

¹⁷MD, PhD, Doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor of Tbilisi State Medical University, Department of Hygiene and Medical Ecology, Tbilisi, Georgia,

¹⁸MD, PhD, Doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor of Tbilisi State Medical University, Tbilisi, Georgia,

¹⁹MD, PhD, Doctor Medical Sciences, Professor of the Division of Dentistry of International School of Medicine at Alte University, Tbilisi, Georgia,

²⁰MD, PhD, Doctor of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Associate Professor of Biological Chemistry Department at National University of Pharmacy, Kharkiv, Ukraine.

ABSTRACT

Aim of the research was to study the key issue aspects of characteristics of key issue aspects of pharmacists' profession, achievements, enhancement, challenges, inclination and perspectives in pharmaceutics and medicine in general based on the sunlight of social pharmacy. Research objectives are materials of

sociological research: the study was quantitative investigation by using survey (Questionnaire). The in-depth interview method of the respondents was used in the study. According the study results in Georgia, for the first time have been studied: The peculiarities of professional and career improvement strategy for pharmacists; Pharmacist specialist' professional features; Factors which most of all had influence on pharmacists' profession(occupational) choice; Pharmacists' professional satisfaction, Pharmacists' career satisfaction; Pharmacists' work satisfaction, satisfaction of the balance between the pharmacists' workload and the pharmacists' personal life, pharmacist' work satisfaction by the time duration of job, pharmacist' satisfaction by income; Professional peculiarities of student pharmacists, Professional peculiarities of employed pharmacists student, Professional peculiarities of the pharmacists with the vision of the chief (head), Peculiarities of professional for pharmacists, viewed by the health-care specialists' Pharmacists' professional features, viewed by the customer's (customer's) eyes; Professional peculiarities of young pharmacist specialist. First time in Georgia scientifically grounded was studied the process of professional formation of pharmacists in the context of pharmaceutical care, including the stages of professional development. First time in Georgia were identified the factors, which was very important for pharmacist professional formation. Were study role of pharmacist and were identified of the specific features for the formation of pharmaceutical specialists at various stages. We make comprehensive study, the essence, regularities and peculiarities of the process of professional development of in the context of pharmaceutical care. The pharmacists hold the great condition to satisfy the necessity for health care vocational to ensure effective and safe using of medicines. To do this, pharmacists should suppose higher liability than they at the present time do for the monitoring of pharmacotherapy for the customers, consumers and patients they are serving. That liability goes completely behind the traditional distributing and dispensing practices that have long been the maintenance of pharmacy activities. Pharmacists' liability should be enlarged conclude controlling of the pharmacotherapeutic progression and thereby improve therapeutic outcomes and patients' life quality, advising with doctor prescribers and consolidating with different health care workers and practitioners on behalf of patients. Pharmacists' involvement into pharmaceuticals may consist in drug storage, drug supply, dispensing, manufacturing, formulation, distribution, marketing, quality warranty, licensing, information management, monitoring, development, education, and research. Drug supply and medicine information management system is the main part of pharmaceutical services and proceeds forming the basement of pharmacy activities. The higher pharmaceutical schooling and education hold an appropriate duty and responsibility to generate post-graduate professionals who are qualified and authorized to provide the pharmaceutical care services. Sufficiency results promote to quality warranty by provided that easily approachable working standards.

Keywords: pharmacists,' profession, achievements, challenges, perspectives, pharmaceuticals, medicine, social pharmacy.

THE SCIENTIFIC TALKS OF THE FEATURES RATIONAL ANTIBIOTIC PHARMACOTHERAPY, PHARMACODYNAMICS OF SOME ANTIBIOTICS' AND ANTIBIOTIC RESISTANCE IN MICROBES OF BACTERIAL DISEASES OF THE MUCOUS MEMBRANES AND SKIN OF THE ORAL CAVITY IN GENERAL THERAPEUTIC STRATEGIES AND FUTURE PROSPECTS

Nodar Sulashvili¹, Kakhaber Robakidze², Ketevan Chakhnashvili³, Irma Buchukuri⁴, Lela Grigolia⁵, Veriko Khundzakishvili⁶, Nato Alavidze⁷, Tamar Okropiridze⁸, Igor Seniuk⁹

¹MD, PhD, Doctor of Pharmaceutical and Pharmacological Sciences, Invited Lecturer of Scientific Research-Skills Center at Tbilisi State Medical University, Tbilisi, Georgia,

²MD, PhD, Doctor of Medicine, Professor of Caucasus International University; Tbilisi, Georgia,

³MD, PhDc, Professor, Dean of International Medical School at Alte University; Tbilisi, Georgia,

⁴MD, PhD, Doctor of Medicine, Professor of Petre Shotadze Medical Academy, Tbilisi, Georgia,

⁵MD, PhD, Doctor of Medicine, Professor of Caucasus International University, Tbilisi, Georgia,

⁶MD, PhD, Doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor of Caucasus International University, Tbilisi-Georgia,

⁷MD, PhD, Doctor of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Professor of Akaki Tsereteli State University, Faculty of Medicine, Department of Pharmacy, Kutaisi, Georgia,

⁸MD, PhD, Doctor Medical Sciences, Professor of the Division of Dentistry of International School of Medicine at Alte University, Tbilisi, Georgia,

⁹MD, PhD, Doctor of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Associate Professor of Biological Chemistry Department at National University of Pharmacy, Kharkiv, Ukraine.

ABSTRACT

The aim of the research was to study and analyze the features rational antibiotic pharmacotherapy and antibiotic resistance in microbes of bacterial diseases of the mucous membranes and skin of the oral cavity in general. There are several bacteria, the so-called super bacteria, that are resistant to multiple antibiotics and can be life-threatening, especially in seriously ill and hospitalized patients. This article outlines current treatment strategies used against some important superbugs such as methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus*, carbapenem-resistant Enterobacteriaceae, vancomycin-resistant Enterococcus, multidrug-resistant *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, and multidrug-resistant *Escherichia coli*. Pathogen-targeted therapies reduce bacterial toxicity by altering their virulence factors through specific processes. On the other hand, host-specific therapies limit these superbugs by modulating immune cells, enhancing host cell functions, and altering disease pathology. Several new antibiotics against the world's most important superbugs are on the market or in clinical development. Medicinal plants with potent secondary metabolites can play a key role in treating these superbugs. Nanotechnology has also emerged as a promising option to combat this evil. There is an urgent need to constantly find the best possible treatment strategy against these superbugs, as resistance to new and new antibiotics may emerge in the future. Rational use of antibiotics and maintenance of good hygiene should be practiced among patients. So, considering the world in optimizing antibacterial therapy for patients in multidisciplinary hospitals, it is proposed to carry out a number of organizational and clinical measures to improve the practice of prescribing antibacterial drugs. In particular, to increase the effectiveness of antibiotic therapy patients and slow down the emergence of resistant strains of bacteria, it is necessary to adhere to certain rules. Thus, the appointment of an antimicrobial drug to a patient without a verified diagnosis or with inappropriate nosology, without taking into account the sensitivity of the pathogen to antibacterial agents, insufficient doses of the drug or duration of treatment, ignoring the recommended frequency of its administration and the possibility of interaction with other drugs reduce its activity, lead to the formation of resistant strains. pathogenic microorganisms and worsen the prognosis of the disease.

Keywords: Rational, antibiotic therapy, bacterial diseases, skin, mucous membranes, oral, cavity.

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Website: <https://esif.net>

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